

Public procurement

The role of public procurement in the strategy for resilient food and farming systems in the North of England

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The Northern Food and Farming Network (NFF)

The Northern Food and Farming Network (NFF) is a collaborative initiative focused on advancing regenerative and socially just farming systems in the North of England. The network, events and activities were previously the Northern Real Farming Conference which launched in 2020, and drew inspiration from the Oxford Real Farming Conference, building on its themes to promote transformative, agroecological strategies. Through a mix of virtual and in-person events, the Northern Real Farming Conference brought together farmers, researchers, and stakeholders to reimagine sustainable food systems.

In 2023, the Northern Real Farming Conference (NRFC) undertook a strategy review and as a result transitioned from hosting an annual conference to coordinating collaborative efforts around a northern food system strategy. To reflect this change, NRFC has become Northern Food and Farming - Collaborating for Resilient Food Systems. The co-designed refined vision and new strategy focuses on six key action areas to shape our collective efforts in the North of England. The increase of the procurement of local agroecological products by public and anchor institutions constitutes action area number five.

Northern Food and Farming fosters collaboration and practical knowledge-sharing around ecological resilience, community empowerment, and farming practices that address climate breakdown and biodiversity. The network is committed to long-term systemic change through cooperation, collaboration and community-driven initiatives.

For more information, please visit:
<https://www.northernfoodandfarming.org/>

The Northern Real Farming Conference strategy co-design process and workshops were funded by the Oglesby Charitable Trust.

The coordination of the network and activities is undertaken by LESS (Lancaster District) CIC on behalf of the Northern Food and Farming collaboration group.

This Northern Food Procurement Strategy was developed in collaboration with the FixOurFood research programme, led by the University of York and funded by the Transforming UK Food Systems Strategic Priorities Fund (Grant number BB/ V004581/1).

FixOurFood aims to enable the transformation to a more regenerative food system through a place-based and co-productive research approach.

For more information, please visit: fixourfood.org

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Executive summary

Background and key points

The Northern Real Farming Conference team's work over the past four years has included running participatory conferences, workshops, discussions, and surveys, and other forms of stakeholder engagement. The Northern networks have recently identified six highly intertwined action areas to enable the transition to a resilient food system in the North of England. Aligned with this new strategy, the group is now called Northern Food and Farming: Collaborating for Resilient Food Systems and is a collaborative programme of action to deliver change.

Public food procurement has been identified as one of these action areas (alongside Workforce, Agroecology, Genetic Diversity, Processing/Distribution/Logistics and Land Access).

Public procurement is a powerful lever for transformation change in the food and farming system:

- Public food procurement is a powerful tool to food security. Considerate sourcing promotes resilience in agriculture, enables agroecological food provision and supports both farm businesses and the health and wellbeing in communities in the North of England.
- Positive changes in public procurement enhance food choices by providing accessible and convenient options for all.
- Prioritising sustainable sourcing in public institutions creates structural support to transition to a more sustainable food and farming system overall.

Executive summary

Key challenges

The quality of meals served in public institutions is mostly inadequate.

For example, school meals often fail to meet nutritional standards, with a high prevalence of sugary foods and limited healthy options, leaving many children hungry and reliant on low-nutrition meal deals.

There are structural issues in public food procurement.

Competing policy priorities hinder the alignment of procurement with sustainability goals. Varied decision-making processes among local authorities and reliance on private providers complicates sustainable procurement efforts.

Domestic food production is largely unsustainable.

Current food production methods are inefficient and unsustainable, leading to inadequate supply for balanced meals in public institutions. A shift towards sustainable practices and increase of local agroecological production is needed to improve long-term environmental outcomes and public health.

Infrastructure deficiencies pose a huge additional challenge to local food procurement.

The historical underinvestment in local food production, processing, and distribution infrastructure limits supply chain effectiveness of local agroecological growers and producers. A decline in small processors, such as abattoirs and grain handling facilities, restricts local producers' access to necessary technologies.

Resource constraints are also an issue in public institutions.

Public procurers such as schools often lack the necessary resources for transport, storage, and trained staff, prioritising convenience over quality. Many public kitchens are currently not suited to accommodate fresh food instead of pre-processed items.

A future direction for public procurement to enable a resilient food and farming system in the North:

- Building demand for agroecological products by ensuring access to nutritious meals through public procurement.
- Supporting local farmers and businesses to support agroecological practices to foster a resilient regional agricultural landscape and food production and processing infrastructure.
- Celebrating local production and seasonality by enhancing local sourcing of grains, pulses, oils, and vegetables, which thrive in the climate in the North of England but are currently underutilised despite their essential nutrient content.

Introduction

The Northern Real Farming Conference started out as a conference, a space to dream, to re-think and to share practical experiences of regenerative and socially just ways to farm and bring food to markets and kitchen tables.

Today, we are Northern Food and Farming, a collaboration of people and organisations working together towards a shared vision of food system transformation, as outlined in our Manifesto and strategic themes.

We focus specifically on the North of England and its unique landscapes and cultures. Our work is centred on the coordination of collaborative projects which take action around the six key action areas we identified as crucial for shifting towards more resilient farming systems in the North.

We recognise that the vision of change that we have identified is ambitious and will take time, and that genuine collaboration is the only way to achieve a transition of this nature – this is why we come together as a collective to do the work that we do.

Our strategy and goals are co-owned by our partner organisations and the wider Northern networks and our approach to working together is characterised by:

- Taking a long term, big picture view of the changes needed in food and farming
- Collaborative, not competing agendas
- Celebrating and promoting diversity in all its forms
- Nurturing the agency of local communities and putting their needs at the centre of decisions made about food and farming systems

Introduction

After three years of events, outreach and discussions with the Northern food and farming community, in 2023 NRFC launched a collaborative reflection and review process with the goal of better understanding where we should focus our efforts to realise our vision of a healthy, fair and sustainable food and farming system for the North.

Through a series of participatory workshops, discussion events and surveys, a strategy was developed which will guide the work over the coming 3-5 years. The overall impact that we aim to see is a resilient food system in the North of England, and we underline the importance of collaborative work and action as the foundation for this work.

The remaining elements of the strategy illustrate the routes needed to achieve the overall impact goal. Crucially, the strategy highlights six action areas which we have identified as being key to bringing about a resilient food system in the North of England:

1. **Workforce**
2. **Agroecology**
3. **Genetic diversity**
4. **Processing, distribution and logistics**
5. **Procurement**
6. **Land access**

These action areas will form the focus of the Northern Food and Farming collaboration's work over the coming 3-5 years and you can explore them in more depth on the Northern Food and Farming website.¹

Each action area has a goal and is supported by a series of desired outcomes and activities which we aim to progress by working collaboratively and in partnership over the next 3-5 years.

The contents presented in this report stem from a series of workshops and evidence gathered around action area five – Procurement. With workshops having taken place in November 2023, 'Moving to more regenerative food and farming systems in the North of England' in Leeds and January 2024, 'The Northern menu - procuring sustainable food for the future', the working group brought together organisations from across the food system across the North of England to identify key issues in food production and consumption currently, while establishing principles for the future of food procurement going forward.

Through collaborative discussions, the workshops helped to establish key principles focused on agroecological sourcing that prioritises sustainable, healthy food options for public and anchor institutions. Supporting not only local farmers but also addressing food insecurity and promoting community resilience, four critical areas of sourcing were identified—grains, protein, oils, and vegetables—which is where the group will concentrate their efforts to enhance the procurement process and ensure a more equitable and sustainable food system in the North.

Introduction

A strategy for resilient food and farming systems in the north of England

Six action areas for a sustainable future

1 **Workforce**
The land-based workforce is thriving

2 **Agroecology**
Landscape recovery projects embody good practices in agroecology

3 **Genetic diversity**
Genetic diversity in Northern seeds and breeds has increased

4 **Processing, distribution and logistics**
Capacity has increased in the North for processing and distribution for agroecological produce

5 **Procurement**
Public and anchor institutions' procurement of local agroecological products has increased manifold

6 **Land access**
More agroecological producers have secure, long-term access to land

Public procurement - why it matters

Background

Efforts to encourage sustainable choices have long been a priority in discussions about public health and environmental initiatives. However, many interventions aimed at influencing consumer behaviour towards more sustainable options rely heavily on education and information campaigns. These efforts operate under the assumption that consumers make decisions based on a lack of knowledge about sustainability issues. Yet, despite widespread awareness-raising efforts, studies have shown that simply providing information does not necessarily lead to significant changes in behaviour. This is because our choices are often influenced by a multitude of factors beyond just knowledge, such as daily routines, busy lifestyles, and resource constraints.

Moreover, broader structural factors, including cultural norms, industry standards, and the availability of sustainable options in the market, also shape consumer behaviour. As such, there is a growing recognition of the need for more holistic approaches that take into account the wider social, economic, and environmental contexts in which consumption occurs. Moving away from solely focusing on individual consumer choices, researchers and policymakers are advocating for a more provision-centered approach to influence consumption patterns,² in order to develop more effective interventions for promoting sustainable diets for better health and net zero.

Public institutions, as providers of meals for diverse communities, have a key role to play in leading the transition towards sustainable consumption and production through their food procurement strategies.³ By implementing rigorous sustainability criteria, prioritising local suppliers, and raising awareness about the environmental and social implications of food choices, public institutions can shape the entire food supply chain. Collaborating with stakeholders, maintaining transparency in procurement procedures, and upholding accountability for sustainability objectives further strengthen their influence. Through these initiatives, public institutions can set a precedent, cultivating a more robust and environmentally conscious food system that meets the needs of current and future generations.

Public procurement - why it matters

Scale and influence

Public food procurement represents a significant share of public spending. In the United Kingdom, it translates to a substantial 5.5% of total food sales, amounting to £2.4 billion annually.⁴ A considerable portion of daily sustenance for UK children, approximately 30%, is supplied through public procurement during school hours.

The process of public food procurement involves the acquiring of food for their operations, from selecting suppliers to managing budgets, all with the aim of providing nutritious and safe meals to a large audience. Harnessing the significant buying power of these institutions, this process not only impacts public health but also influences broader food systems and environmental sustainability. Even seemingly small changes in how food is provided can have significant positive effects on pressing environmental issues such as climate change and biodiversity loss. Moreover, procurement can be a means to promote more collaborative and inclusive food policies, involving input from local authorities, producers, and other stakeholders. By shaping food procurement plans, public institutions not only affect the types of food purchased but also impact broader aspects of food production and waste management, making them key players in shaping the food system.⁵

However, despite its significant impact, catering services in schools for example face challenges in aligning sustainability goals with competing policy priorities.

Public procurement - why it matters

Economic leverage

Public institutions, as consistent and sizable buyers, possess the power to reshape economic and agricultural landscapes.

Stipulating elevated production and quality standards from suppliers can unlock a multitude of positive outcomes. Farmers committed to sustainable and environmentally friendly practices, when supported by public procurement, gain economic security. Simultaneously, manufacturers sourcing from such responsible farmers contribute to the production of high-quality, eco-friendly products.

For example, Scandinavian countries have leveraged innovative public procurement policies to boost organic farming.⁶ In Denmark, prioritising organic procurement, public institutions have also set an example for private food services like restaurants and catering companies. This has led to a remarkable five-fold increase in organic sales within the food service sector over a decade. Additionally, the collaboration throughout the organic supply chain has been instrumental in driving a 70 percent increase in organic farmland from 2011 to 2019.⁷ In essence, public kitchens have not only fueled the demand for organic products but have also spurred the growth of organic agriculture in the country.

In the UK, sourcing from local suppliers during the pandemic strengthened local economies and supply chains, and the Food for Life Served Here award increased Scottish meat spending by 12%, supporting higher welfare standards and the local food economy.^{8,9}

As opposed to this, weak procurement standards risk hindering progress - for example by allowing caged eggs in public kitchens, despite the UK market's shift towards free-range eggs.¹⁰

Public procurement - why it matters

Public health impact

The impact of sustainable public food procurement resonates profoundly in public health outcomes.

A recent study highlights the difficulties Yorkshire students face with Free School Meals, including inconsistent meal allowances, confusing pricing, reliance on unhealthy meal deals with sugary drinks, and a lack of vegetables in quick options like sandwiches and pizza.¹¹ Conversely, offering nutritious meals in schools and hospitals ensures equal access for everyone, setting the foundation for health and well-being. Institutions serving healthier meals, beyond the benefits for individuals, foster equal access to nutritious food, resulting in improved public health and reduced healthcare costs, contributing to healthier, resilient and thriving communities.^{12,13}

Public procurement - why it matters

Long-term environmental benefits

A strategic focus on agroecological production systems for balanced and seasonal meals in public food procurement sets the stage for profound environmental benefits and agroecological production. A framework that incorporates both the regulatory aspects of organic farming and the innovative practices of regeneration, fosters a more environmentally sustainable and resilient food system. It does so by enhancing soil health, promoting biodiversity, reducing reliance on chemical inputs, conserving water resources, supporting local food systems and increasing resilience to climate change. Farmers in the North are increasingly adopting low-input farming practices and enhancing the ecological integrity and regenerative capacity of their agricultural systems. However, they encounter significant challenges in establishing connections with local buyers, which impedes their ability to effectively distribute produce to local communities. As demand for food produced to sustainable standards rises, and public institutions become reliable buyers of produce from Northern farmers, more farmers will transition to agroecological practices. The ensuing improvements in soil quality, healthier ecosystems and reduced environmental impact of industrial agriculture underscore the long-term ecological gains.

It is important to note here the synergies between human health and the health of our planet.¹⁴ It is scientifically proven that eating to provide all the necessary nutrients for our well-being also supports production methods which respect the limits of our planet's resources. Most prominently, by emphasising plant-based foods and reducing the consumption of animal products, particularly red meat, diets promote both individual health and environmental sustainability. This shift towards a more plant-centric diet not only reduces the risk of chronic diseases like obesity and heart disease but also helps mitigate environmental issues like climate change, land degradation, and water scarcity.

In a recent study, different models of school meal procurement in five European countries were evaluated to understand their impact on environmental, economic, and nutritional outcomes. Surprisingly, while the procurement contracts focused heavily on factors like local and organic sourcing, the study found that the nutritional standards of the meals played a more significant role in reducing carbon emissions than these sourcing criteria. Essentially, policies aimed at improving child health and nutrition unintentionally led to positive environmental outcomes in school meal services.¹⁵ This highlights the importance of refining public food procurement contracts to better prioritise environmental goals alongside nutritional standards

Economic opportunities and job creation

Embracing sustainable agriculture in public procurement creates job opportunities across farming, processing, distribution, and preparation of agroecological products. This not only benefits rural communities by skilling up the workforce and improving workers' well being across the supply chain, from farms ¹⁶ to kitchens ¹⁷ but also aligns with broader goals of levelling up.

By leveraging the economic influence of public institutions and aligning policies with ecological and health objectives, we have the potential to shape a future for the North that is economically robust, environmentally resilient, and socially equitable.

Food production and provision

The status quo

The current situation of meal provision through public procurement in the North of England

In many schools across the North, the food eaten by children in schools is inadequate from a nutrition perspective. A study conducted at the University of Leeds found that less than 2% of packed lunches consumed by children in English primary schools meet nutritional standards,¹⁸ highlighting concerns about the quality of food provided to students. While there has been a decrease in the amount of sugary foods in lunch boxes over the past decade, it remains higher than recommended, with a decline in essential vitamins and minerals – a shortcoming which is attributed to the lack of fresh food. Only one in five children include vegetables or salad in their packed lunch, with them predominantly consisting of sweet and savoury snacks and sugary drinks, raising concerns about children's nutrition and the risk of obesity. Similarly, a recent study conducted by the University of York in collaboration with the Food Foundation has highlighted that meals provided in school canteens are often of insufficient nutritional value. In regard to free school meals, which provide the only hot meal a day to many, it has been found that offerings are very limited, limiting students' food choices and leaving them hungry during the day, highlighting the need to ensure that all children can access nutritious meals in schools.¹⁹ These circumstances highlight the inadequacy of current public spending on school food and the urgent need for more effective public procurement strategies to ensure that the resources allocated are used to provide healthy, sustainably sourced food for all young people in education, fostering equality in access to nutritious meals and supporting children's immediate health and long-term well-being.

A recent study focused on North Yorkshire Education Service's catering services highlighted the key role of local authorities in shaping the food supply chains for school meals, with their decisions impacting the entire school food system. The case study reveals a dispersed system²⁰ where strategic objectives and menus are determined by NYES Catering, while North Yorkshire County Council handles procurement and supplier contracts. Although around 40% of schools are supplied by local authorities, the decision to use public sector catering or private providers varies. The study suggests that involving local businesses and small to medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in procurement could address issues of environmental sustainability, lack of traceability and accountability. By enabling local authorities to procure more sustainably, not only do they support suppliers implementing sustainable practices, but they also improve school children's access to healthy, sustainable food.

Food production and provision

The status quo

Sustainability of food production in the UK and the North of England

Local food production, processing and distribution infrastructure

Long-term extensive research with local food producers at the University of York shows a keen desire of both farmers and small and medium sized enterprises in the food sector to shorten supply chains and keep food local.²¹ Currently, there is considerable optimism regarding the development of online stores for buyers as part of the implementation of improved public food procurement.²² These online platforms would be curated to feature products that meet the latest government buying standards, facilitating easier access to goods from local, sustainable food enterprises for public sector anchor institutions. This digital approach aims to streamline the procurement process and enhance transparency by allowing buyers to see and select local produce more efficiently.

However, despite the evident advantages of local food systems based on agroecological principles, enterprises keen to operate within short and local supply chains face substantial challenges due to the historical lack of investment into adequate infrastructure for processing, storage and transportation. This deficiency is evident across the food industry, with the number of processors having rapidly declined over the past years, to the point that for many products there are only a few major processors left, making it increasingly difficult for local producers to access food processing technologies such as mills or abattoirs. While the decline of small abattoirs has received frequent attention by various campaigns²³ and media outlets,²⁴ the decline of grain handling, processing and storage facilities for example, has, apart from the lockdown period,²⁵ been less publicised.

Independent producers across all sectors in the food system are constrained by few available channels and face the dilemma of either selling their products to the global market or, paradoxically, transporting their goods across the country, with impacts on costs, carbon emissions and additional strain on the workforce, all in the effort to keep food supplies local.

While there is interest and effort from local producers to supply fresh, agroecological food to public institutions, structural challenges within the food system - such as inadequate infrastructure, staff training, and reliance on pre-processed food - hinder these efforts. Even when individual producers adapt to meet institutional needs, systemic gaps like transportation, storage, and kitchen facilities make it difficult for such collaborations to succeed. As a result, addressing these infrastructure challenges at multiple levels is crucial for enabling more sustainable food systems. This is aggravated by the fact that many public procurers lack the necessary resources themselves, such as transport, storage and cooking facilities and adequately trained staff. Facilities and resources available in public canteens are often set up to accommodate the use of pre-prepared or partially processed food items, prioritising convenience over cooking from scratch. A platform that allows local canteens to connect with local producers, such as the suggestion of an online portal, as suggested by the Dixon Foundation (DPUK) is welcomed,²⁶ however, on its own it will be of little help, when basic infrastructure on and between various levels of the system is severely lacking.

Food production and provision

The status quo

Issues in the food system

Food production in the UK overall is highly inefficient and unsustainable, there simply is not enough food being produced to put sustainable and balanced meals on plates served in schools, hospitals and other public institutions. Although over 70% of the UK's land is used for agricultural production,²⁷ the proportion of land on which food is produced under sustainable, agroecological production methods is almost negligible. Only 3% of the total farmed area on agricultural holdings in the UK being is used for organic production.²⁸ Instead, resources are focussed on industrial livestock production, which has the single worst impact on the food system and the environment.²⁹ About 40% of the UK's arable land is used to grow grains as feed for industrial livestock production. With a remaining net dependency on imports of about 25% of total feed cost, this still only represents a proportion of the amount of feed currently required by the conventional UK livestock industry. In 2020 alone, livestock farmers spent £5.6 billion on 30 million tonnes animal feed in 2020, making animal feed account for the single largest input cost for UK agriculture.³⁰

Thus, from a calorie standpoint, our use of land in the UK appears highly inefficient.³¹ 85% of the farmland that feeds the UK, both domestically and overseas, is dedicated to rearing animals, however, meat, dairy, and eggs only contribute 32% of the calories we consume. In contrast, the 15% of farmland used to grow plant crops for human consumption provides a whopping 68% of our calories.

Agriculture in the North

There is a stark contrast in the distribution of organic food producers across regions of England, with the Northern regions notably lagging behind their Southern counterparts. While the South West region holds a substantial proportion of organic producers, comprising nearly 30% of the total, the North of England - encompassing the North West, North East, and Yorkshire & The Humber regions - presents a concerning underrepresentation in the organic sector, accounting for only about 8% of overall producers.³² This striking disparity highlights a significant imbalance in the organic food production landscape, which does not only affect availability of local high quality food, but also the wider health of the Northern environment and its people. Intensive agriculture, as practised widely in our region, contributes to soil compaction and erosion, reducing the land's ability to absorb water and increasing the risk of surface runoff during heavy rainfall events, contributing to for example the severity and frequency of flood events.³³ Effective land management practices,³⁴ including sustainable agricultural techniques and floodplain management strategies, are essential for mitigating such environmental risks. Public Procurement from local sustainable suppliers can be a key lever to enable a transition to support more agroecological farming methods in the North.

Northern food production and provision

The future

Local and agroecological products in public and anchor institutions' procurement

Sourcing principles for economically, environmentally, socially sustainable and healthy public meals

Public procurement is a powerful tool to build resilience in the local food system, encouraging the use of local land for the production of sustainable, healthy produce. The goal is not isolationism or unrealistic self-sufficiency but rather leveraging procurement to combat current issues in the ways in which food is produced and distributed and to create a resilient regional agricultural landscape. Localising public procurement supports local farmers and businesses, promoting social justice and economic resilience, while ensuring nutritious meals reach communities across the region.

The North of England is rich in resources and potential, but not everything can be produced locally, and trade remains essential for accessing a diverse array of goods, fostering economic interdependence. In our pursuit of sustainability, we need to recognise that carbon emissions and aims for Net Zero are critical factors.

Realistically, certain products cannot be produced locally due to climate constraints or the inherent nature of the agricultural landscape. Efforts to strengthen local supply chains must align with wider strategies, recognising that "quality" does not always equate to sustainability. While reducing food miles is often pushed as an environmental incentive for local procurement, it is important to note that food miles represent a poor indicator for the environmental and ethical impacts of food.³⁵ For instance, importing fresh tomatoes from Southern Europe may result in lower overall carbon emissions than growing them locally in heated greenhouses. Trade is important, as it allows access to a diverse array of goods and fosters economic interdependence. A realistic, sustainable approach focuses on what grows well locally and supports those crops - to be grown through agroecological methods, while accepting that trade and diverse imports are still important for overall food security and sustainability.

Agroecological production principles take precedence, and public procurement needs to prioritise sustainability principles rather than solely aiming for 100% local sourcing. These principles are explained in more detail in the following pages.

Northern food production and provision

The future

Sustainable sourcing: A holistic approach for institutions

Economy

Sustainable sourcing from an economic perspective prioritises supporting small, diverse, and progressive producers. It means helping such producers establishing viable routes to market while ensuring fair compensation throughout the supply chain. This includes implementing real living wages and exploring profit-sharing mechanisms to enhance employee engagement. Institutions can consider adopting models like Community Interest Companies (CIC) or cooperatives and collaborate with similar entities along the supply chain to strengthen collective impact. The revenue generated should be reinvested into organisations to enhance sustainability, with funds channelled towards ethical suppliers, renewable energy, and environmentally friendly machinery.

Environment

Sustainable sourcing principles in relation to the environment advocate for sourcing raw ingredients from certified producers, emphasising organic certifications and evidence of agroecological production methods. They prioritise growers and producers who work to high environmental standards. Low emissions, land regeneration, and biodiversity conservation is crucial. They avoid sourcing from factory farming operations and seek alternatives to high-impact ingredients such as industrially produced meat, dairy, and palm oil and support environmental conservation efforts. Sustainable operations within sourcing institutions involve minimising emissions in production and packaging, as well as reducing waste through efficient processes and sustainable packaging materials. By adhering to these principles, institutions can contribute to preserving ecosystems and mitigating climate change.

Social equality

In the social realm, sustainable sourcing seeks to expand access to a diverse range of social groups, particularly marginalised communities often excluded from premium markets. This involves addressing structural barriers to affordability and availability, while fostering inclusivity and diversity in product offerings. By prioritising social equity and access, institutions can play a role in reshaping societal norms and contributing to more inclusive, resilient communities.

Nutrition and health

Sustainable sourcing principles in nutrition and health underscore the importance of ingredient quality, simplicity, and nutritional value in product formulation. Prioritising high-quality ingredients from agroecological production methods and avoiding or minimising ingredients low in nutrition supports community health and wellbeing. Incorporating seasonal variety and promoting nutrient balance by reducing added sugar, sodium, and fat in products further enhances their health-conscious appeal. Additionally, exploring alternative protein sources encourages diversification of nutritional options, aligning with evolving dietary preferences and promoting sustainable food systems.

Northern food production and provision

The future

Leveraging public procurement for a resilient food and farming system in the North of England

Public procurement plays a crucial role in building resilient local food systems by leveraging its significant purchasing power to drive demand for agroecological products and support sustainable agricultural practices.

By prioritising locally sourced, seasonal, and nutritious foods, public institutions can create stable markets for regional farmers, encouraging them to adopt environmentally friendly practices. This approach strengthens local supply chains, fosters economic security for growers and producers, and reduces reliance on unsustainable options. In this way, public procurement can also enhance public health outcomes, providing access to nutritious meals in schools and hospitals, while also promoting environmental stewardship by reducing carbon emissions and supporting agroecological farming practices.

Through these mechanisms, public procurement becomes an effective lever to develop the other five NFF action areas and a means to foster a more resilient, sustainable, and equitable food system.

Local food sourcing and institutional responsibility

Local food sourcing celebrates the diverse crops that thrive in local climates as well as seasonality. Prioritising sourcing agroecological produce from the region promotes biodiversity and reduces the environmental impact in the immediate environment and strengthens local economies. Choosing seasonal produce ensures we enjoy the freshest and most nutritious foods while minimising carbon footprints from transportation. Local agroecology-based food systems can fill the gaps left by conventional systems, materially but also socially, fostering community trust and resilience.

For public procurement to enable resilience in the local food and farming system, it is most important for institutions to adjust their menus according to what can be produced locally, considering also seasonality. This means being mindful of what foods are available in the area and making sure that the institution's food supply aligns with local production. It is not just about nutritional value; it is also about recognising when certain foods are at their freshest and most abundant. So, menus and shopping lists should be planned with the region's production capacity and the seasonal availability of foods in mind. This approach ensures that the institution is supporting local farmers and offering the freshest and most sustainable options to its communities.³⁶

Northern food production and provision

The future

A future direction for public procurement to enhance a resilient food and farming system in the North of England involves several key strategies

- First, building demand for agroecological products can be achieved by prioritising access to nutritious public meals. This approach not only supports healthier diets but also promotes agroecological farming practices.
- Additionally, supporting local farmers and businesses in adopting agroecological methods is crucial for fostering a resilient regional agricultural landscape. This includes strengthening food production and processing infrastructure to ensure long-term resilience for sustainable farm businesses.
- Lastly, public procurement should celebrate local production and seasonality by prioritising the sourcing of nutrient-rich crops, which are well-suited to the region's climate.

By focusing on these strategies, public procurement can play a critical role in developing a resilient food system in the North of England.

A northern menu

Four identified focal areas to enhance resilient food and farming systems in the North of England through targeted public procurement practices

The North of England has significant potential for enhancing local sourcing in four critical food categories:

1. **Grains**
2. **Proteins (pulses)**
3. **Oils**
4. **Vegetables**

Production of these food categories evidently works well in the climatic conditions of the North of England, but is currently underutilised, or primarily utilised with unsustainable methods and disconnected from local processing and distribution system and not accessible to local communities.

Each food category contributes to a balanced diet (grains for carbohydrates, pulses for proteins, oils for fats, and vegetables for vitamins and minerals). Promoting agroecological production and local sourcing in these categories fosters a more holistic approach to resilience in the Northern food system, empowering local growers and fostering the consumption of sustainable and nutritious meals, which presents a substantial opportunity for public procurement.

A northern menu

Northern grains

Grains, particularly wheat, have historically been a cornerstone of UK diets, serving as a primary energy source and contributing significantly to the nation's food intake, environment, and economy. Wheat alone constitutes around 30% of the daily food energy intake per person in the UK.³⁷ With an average flour consumption of 54kg per person per year and bread consumption of 562g per person per week,³⁸ wheat's importance in the UK diet cannot be overstated. Despite its significance, grains are often undervalued and underappreciated, with a large portion of bread consumed being white bread, which lacks essential fibre, vitamins, and minerals. Most bread is mass-produced using the Chorleywood bread process,³⁹ with a significant portion of it ending up as wasted food,⁴⁰ contributing to inefficiencies in consumption.

It has been estimated that the amount of wheat and oats grown across the UK currently being fed to animals is equivalent to 10.7 billion loaves of bread and 5.8 billion bowls of porridge.⁴¹ Both in the North East as well as in the Yorkshire and Humber region, wheat products generate the highest monetary value of agricultural production, and cereal growing represents the most prominent farming type after grazing livestock (about one fifth in the North East⁴² and about one third in Yorkshire).⁴³ However, most of the grains grown are not made accessible for people to eat, but are used as animal fodder.

Northern farmers have been showing that the land is suitable to grow grains for high-quality flours, highlighting the potential for greater appreciation and sustainable consumption, highlighting the potential for greater appreciation and sustainable consumption of grains. Organisations like the Yorkshire Grain Alliance⁴⁴ comprised of farmers, millers, and bakers dedicated to working with heritage and population grains, are leading the way in this effort.

By leveraging changes in public procurement practices to empower local growers and millers, we can enhance the availability of better-quality grains in Northern communities, supporting both local agriculture and healthier food options for residents.

A northern menu

Northern protein

The UK currently produces over 700,000 tonnes of pulses per year,⁴⁵ primarily destined for animal feed or export to the Middle East. However, there is a growing recognition that increasing pulse consumption and production domestically could have numerous benefits, including promoting healthier diets, reducing reliance on imports, enhancing biodiversity, supporting local economies, and mitigating the environmental impact of agriculture. In the catering sector, there's a notable shift towards plant-based offerings, driven by commitments to reducing carbon emissions.

Major contract caterers such as Aramark, Compass Group, Elior, ISS, and Sodexo are adapting their menus towards more plant-based options and committing to reducing meat consumption. While these commitments vary in specificity, they reflect a broader industry-wide trend towards plant-centric diets aligned with environmental sustainability goals.⁴⁶ However, the majority of the ingredients for these meals are currently imported, and many of them would be classified as ultra processed foods.

With the growing momentum within the catering sector, there is an opportunity for local authorities in the North to prioritise a shift towards incorporating more fava beans and other pulses into their menus. Embracing fava beans, for example, offers countless benefits that align with economic, environmental and social priorities of our region, including environmental sustainability, supporting local economies, and fostering healthier communities. By sourcing and serving locally and sustainably grown fava beans, public institutions can significantly increase their impact on building environmental resilience in the North. Moreover, investing in local bean production supports regional agricultural economies, creating opportunities for farmers and contributing to the resilience of rural communities. Furthermore, normalising the consumption of fava beans among Northern communities positively contributes to public health outcomes, as these legumes are rich in essential nutrients and offer a sustainable source of plant-based protein.

Therefore, by embracing agroecologically produced fava, or other beans on their plates, public procurement institutions in the North can play a critical role in advancing sustainability, supporting local livelihoods, and promoting the well-being of our communities.

A northern menu

Northern oils

With the Mediterranean facing unprecedented challenges due to climate change, the stability of olive oil production is under threat,⁴⁷ leading to soaring prices and concerns about the future of this beloved ingredient.

In regions across Spain, Italy, and Greece, where olive oil has long been a culinary cornerstone, farmers are grappling with reduced yields and escalating costs, resulting in a significant impact on global markets. As prices continue to rise, consumers and chefs alike are feeling the pinch, prompting creative solutions in the kitchen and a search for alternative cooking oils. However, amidst this crisis, there lies an opportunity for the UK to bolster its own agricultural sector and reduce dependency on imported olive oil.

The UK is already producing over a million tonnes of oilseed rape per year.⁴⁸ While much of this is produced with industrial farming methods, such large-scale cultivation of oilseed rape can lead to biodiversity loss, soil degradation, and harm to bees and other beneficial insects. Additionally, the use of pesticides and genetic modification in its production has sparked debates about the long-term effects on ecosystems and human health. However, by investing in the production of high-quality rapeseed oil,⁴⁹ which boasts similar health benefits and culinary versatility, the UK can not only ensure a stable supply of cooking oil for its citizens but also support local growers and millers.

With suitable infrastructure and government support, gearing up production of agroecologically produced rapeseed oil could be a game-changer, bringing better quality cooking oils to Northern communities and strengthening the resilience of the UK's food system in the face of global challenges.

A northern menu

Northern vegetables

Currently, the UK's self-sufficiency in vegetables is below 50%,⁵⁰ however, we have some fantastic vegetable growers in the North who produce a large variety of delicious and nutritious vegetables through agroecological methods. Shifting towards consuming more locally sourced vegetables means that different types of vegetables will be available throughout different times of the year.

Unlike imported or non-local vegetables available year-round in supermarkets, locally sourced vegetables are typically harvested at their peak ripeness and are in sync with the natural growing seasons. This means that certain vegetables may only be available during specific times of the year when they can be harvested locally in abundance.

Embracing local vegetable consumption encourages us to adapt our diets to enjoy a variety of fresh produce that changes with the seasons. For instance, in the summer, we might indulge in juicy tomatoes and crisp cucumbers, while in the winter, we savour hearty root vegetables like carrots, parsnips, and potatoes. Adapting to seasonal eating not only connects us more closely with the natural rhythms of agriculture but also promotes a diverse and nutritious diet that celebrates the unique flavours and textures of each season.

With public procurement in the North focusing on local sourcing, this shift towards seasonal vegetable consumption becomes an opportunity to support local farmers and promote environmental sustainability while enjoying the freshest and most flavourful vegetables available.

Next steps

This document presents a collective vision for public food procurement for agroecologically grown produce in the North of England.

Moving towards concrete next steps, the Northern Food and Farming network will build on existing insights to continue to foster action across the food system. Follow-up workshops will focus on working with key stakeholders to explore the feasibility of scaling up agroecological production in the key identified areas, initiating the groundwork for a larger value chain collaboration into public procurement, with an initial focus on legume production and procurement through a project funded by Farming the Future.

A series of events will take place to progress from conceptual discussions to the practical development of a Northern food future enabled through public procurement.

Sign up to the Northern Food and Farming newsletter via the [website](#) to be kept up to date.

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Acknowledgements

This report has been co-created and the authors would like to acknowledge and thank the wider Northern Food and Farming community for their input in shaping the themes and discussions.

The outcomes of two workshops in particular played a significant role in shaping the direction of this report. Firstly, the NRFC strategy event 'Moving to more regenerative food and farming systems in the North of England' on 6 November 2023 in Leeds, which included two working group discussions exploring the role of public procurement in helping to shift towards more resilient food systems in the North of England. We thank and acknowledge all who contributed to those .

A follow-up workshop, 'The Northern menu - procuring sustainable food for the future', then took place on 18 January 2024 in Leeds and created a series of actions of which this report is one. We are grateful to, and acknowledge the input of, the following colleagues and friends who participated in that workshop, including: Sonja Woodcock, FoodWise Leeds; Selina Treuherz, Sheffood; Neil Boyle, University of Leeds; Claire Dalton Nobbs, Leeds City Council; Kirstie Lamb, City of Doncaster Council; Rosie Atkins, FeedLeeds Farm Group; Nicholas Wilkinson, University of Leeds; Silvia Rossi, FoodFutures; Aine Douglas, Calderdale Food Network; Rebecca St Clair, University of Leeds; Claire Gribben, University of Leeds; Barbara Rhodes, Micklefield Community Green Group; Alison Morgan; Derek Prest, Leeds City Council; Andrew White, Leeds City Council

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DOI:

[10.5281/zenodo.13935153](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13935153)